

Together,
there's
something
science
can do.

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[Demand for European patents exceeds 200 000 for the first time:](#) For the first time, European patents reached a record high in 2025, with over 200,000 applications filed. Growth was driven mainly by digital technologies such as AI, quantum computing, and 6G communications, as well as electrical apparatuses such as batteries and semiconductors. While the U.S. and Germany remain leading sources of applications, China has risen to the top three. Furthermore, while large corporations dominate applications filings, SMEs and universities play an increasingly significant role.

[New molecular editing tool to relocate alcohol groups developed:](#) MIT researchers have developed a new molecular “editing” technique that moves alcohol functional groups within a molecule without having to rebuild it from scratch. Using decatungstate, a light-activated catalyst, the method precisely relocates alcohol groups while preserving the molecule’s 3D structure and predictability, overcoming a major bottleneck where even small structural changes previously required costly, time-consuming resynthesis. As it works on complex, late-stage molecules, it is especially valuable for drug development. Overall, the technique enables faster, more efficient design of pharmaceuticals, materials, and chemicals by allowing fine-tuned modifications of existing molecules.

[Scientists launch open-access framework to rapidly evaluate climate models:](#) The Rapid Evaluation Framework (REF) is an open-access tool designed to speed up the assessment of climate models. The REF automatically compares climate model outputs with real-world observations to provide immediate and efficient insights into the models’ accuracy. In the past, evaluations could take months and require massive data downloads, but the REF now streamlines and automates this process. The REF will support upcoming climate assessments, and its results are publicly available, helping researchers and policymakers access more reliable and up-to-date climate projections.

[New US Tariffs on imports of pharmaceutical products and ingredients:](#) As of July 31, 2026, the US will apply new tariffs targeting imported pharmaceutical products ranging from 10% to 20% *ad valorem* duty. The stated goal of the Trump administration is to protect domestic industries and to address trade imbalances in the US. Due to these tariffs, however, businesses importing pharmaceuticals into the US must reassess costs, compliance obligations, and sourcing strategies. The drug industry has sharply criticized the tariffs, calculating that they [will cost the US US\\$51 billion annually](#).